

Diplomacy of the Emirate of Bukhara during the Time of Amir Heydar

Turayeva is the daughter of Charos Kurbanmurat ¹

¹ National University of Uzbekistan, 4th year student of the Faculty of History

Abstract:

In this article, the history of diplomacy, foreign policy, embassy relations, development of trade, including friendship with Russia, mutual cooperation and development of economic and social spheres of the Bukhara Emirate during the reign of Amir Haydar are analyzed with the help of scientific.

Keywords: Amir Heydar, Alexander I, Azimjon Muminjonov, Grigory Semenovich Volkonsky, military governor-general of Orenburg, Troisk.

At the end of the 18th and the beginning of the 19th century, relations between the Bukhara Emirate and the Russian Empire were mainly characterized by the development of trade, embassy and diplomatic relations. At the beginning of the 19th century, as a result of the development of diplomatic relations between Bukhara and Russia, the growth of trade, the issue of security on trade routes and the further development of trade relations became one of the main tasks of the two countries. After all, there is enough information about the mutual cooperation of the Bukhara Emirate with Russia and the active diplomatic relations, both in Eastern and Western sources, and the correspondence of the emirs is well preserved. During the 19th century, ambassadors were usually sent to discuss political and economic relations or to provide information on important events, and their purpose was stated in the emir label.

During the period of Amir Haydar, the internal politics of the Bukhara Emirate was not stagnant, and the main goal of the foreign policy was the rights of strong diplomatic partners and Bukhara merchants, and there were a number of embassy exchanges to facilitate them in the territory of Russia. During the reign of Amir Heydar, he tried to further strengthen diplomatic relations with countries such as Khiva, Kokan Khanate, Russia, Iran, China, Afghanistan, Turkey, in order to form

political-legal and economic relations. and stands out as a head of state who has achieved a number of successes in the fight against external opposition¹.

Amir Haidar (1800 - 1826) sat on the throne of Movarounnahr in 1218 (1802) with the title of "Amir Syed". Amir Haydar spends his reign with non-stop military campaigns, battles and suppressing rebellions. He cannot reach the level of his father in terms of religious haste, perverted beliefs and bigotry².

During the foreign policy of Amir Haydar, relations with Russia were good, and the main reasons for this were good cooperation in trade and trade and seeing it as a strong support. In 1801, spun yarn worth 483.7 thousand soums was exported from Bukhara to Russia, which is 68% of the total trade, cotton trade worth 19.5 thousand soums 2%, gauze trade worth 42.5 thousand soums 5%, raw leather trade worth 101.7 thousand soums 13%, 45,800 soums of karakol trade was 6%, 25,700 soums of rhubarb trade was 3%, and other types of products were 3% of the trade volume. From this information, we can see that spun yarn was a very necessary raw material for Russian industry, and trade with Bukhara was also beneficial for them.

In 1801, gold worth 217,700 soums was exported from Russia to Bukhara, which was 40% of the total trade volume. 112,000 soums of wool and other textile goods accounted for 25% of the trade, 76,000 soums for 15% of the fur trade, 16,000 soums for 3% of the leather trade, and other types of goods were also exported, which made up 5% of the total trade. Among the raw materials coming from Russia, metal had a special place and was in high demand in Central Asia, because the mining industry was not well developed. Until the beginning of the 19th century, the export of metals to Central Asia was prohibited, but as a result of active trade, this ban was lifted. With the growth of trade relations between Bukhara and Russia, the diplomatic relations between the two countries are getting stronger, and during the period of Amir Haidar, the Bukhara Emirate was active in foreign policy. sends ambassadors as a leader. In turn, Russia was also interested in diplomatic relations, sending a large diplomatic mission under the leadership of Goverdovsky in 1803, Abdulnasir Subhonkulov in 1809, and A. F. Negri in 1820³.

Embassy relations between Russia and Bukhara are conducted on the basis of various topics, proposals and, of course, goals. In 1805, one of the Russian confidants, Khabibulla Abdulov, was sent from Orenburg to Bukhara in the guise of a merchant on the instructions of the head of the Russian Ministry of Foreign Affairs, Prince Adam Charteriysky. Nadirshah's grandson, who was supposed to live in Bukhara, was to be taken to Alexander I. In 1805, the ambassadors of the Bukhara Emirate - Mirzabek Allayorov, Gofurjon Navrozkhoyayev - arrived in Orenburg, they handed over the equipment confiscated from Valit Khamitov, who was engaged in forging money in Bukhara, to the governor-general of Orenburg, but due to the fact that these merchants did not have the necessary documents confirming the authority of the embassy, they do not allow them to meet with the heads of the Russian state⁴

In 1809, another confidant, Poruchik Odilnasir Subhonkulov, came to Bukhara from Russia, and he was entrusted with the secret mission of the military governor of Orenburg. Subhankulov's tasks include solving the problem of trade caravans robbed by pirates while ensuring the security of caravan trade between the Bukhara Emirate and the Russian states, fighting against organized crime in cooperation between Russia and the Bukhara states, and handing over counterfeiter Khamitov

¹Ж.М.Шодиев. Бухоро амирлиги давлатчилигининг ривожланиши. – Тошкент.; ТДЮИ “Тезкор нашр марказида”. 2010. Б – 45.

²Armini Vamberi Buxoro yohud Movarounnahr tarixi (ikkinchi jild). – Т.:Info capital group,2019. 171-172 - В

³А Р Мухамеджанов, Т Нигматов. Бухоро ва хеванинг россия билан муносабатлари тарихига доир баъзи манбалар. – Т.; Ўзбекистон ССР Фанлар Академияси. 1957. 13 - Б

⁴Ж.М.Шодиев. Бухоро амирлиги давлатчилигининг ривожланиши. – Тошкент.; ТДЮИ “Тезкор нашр марказида”. 2010. Б –45-46.

and his associates to the Russian state. dealt with the issues, but the amir does not like that such issues are taking place on the basis of the orders and instructions of the military governor of Orenburg. Amir Haidar is forced to send a letter to express his displeasure to the Russian emperor, who humiliates Bukhara and does not see the amir as his equal. Amir Khaidar's letter states that such issues should be resolved only by the heads of the two countries and that the head of the Russian state should address the amir. The main goals of the Emirate of Bukhara were to maintain the reputation of an independent state at the international level, as well as the observance of international laws and regulations of embassy relations. On the basis of agreements between the two countries, criminal-legal assistance will be provided, the criminal group led by Valit Khamidov will be found at the disposal of the Russian state, and information will be given to Subhonkulov about who distributed the fake money and through which means. Adilnasir Subhonkulov managed to free 3 Russian prisoners captured in Bukhara⁵.

Amir Heydar wants to increase the status of the Bukhara Emirate through diplomatic agreements in foreign policy, and will continue to send ambassadors to neighboring regions and countries with great influence on the world scale. He tries to promote relations with the Russian Empire, which is the main and useful partner in trade, in this regard, the official visit of the Emirate of Bukhara to Russia takes place in 1815. The goal of the second embassy was to reach Turkey through Russian territory, further develop trade relations, and protect the rights of Bukhara merchants at customs.

In conclusion, it can be said that during the reign of Amir Haydar, political instability and uprisings against the central government increased significantly. Even the emir's own brother rebelled against him. Relations with the Khanate of Khiva were also hostile. The battle with Eltuzar Khan, the plundering campaign of Muhammad Rahim Khan I, and the truce signed in 1825 could not completely improve the differences between the two countries. Amir Haydar strives to strengthen foreign policy through diplomatic channels, focusing on getting closer to the Russian Empire, which is far ahead of the Central Asian countries in development, and by improving diplomatic relations. Both countries seek reciprocal benefits from diplomatic relations, with the Russian Empire benefiting the most. Amir Haidar will leave a name in the history of Bukhara Emirate as a skilled diplomat ruler.

REFERENCES:

1. А Р Мухамеджанов, Т Нигматов. Бухоро ва хеванинг россия билан муносабатлари тарихига доир баъзи манбалар. – Т.; Ўзбекистон ССР Фанлар Академияси. 1957.
2. Ж.М.Шодиев. Бухоро амирлиги давлатчилигининг ривожланиши. – Тошкент.; ТДЮИ “Тезкор нашр марказида”. 2010.
3. Мирза Абдалазим Сомий. Тарих-и салатин-и мангитийа (“История мангитских государей”). – Москва: Издвост лит.; 1962.
4. Arminiy Vamberi Buxoro yohud Movarounnahr tarixi (ikkinchi jild). – Т.:Info capital group,2019.
5. Zamonov A T, Egamberdiyev A. Buxoro amirligi tarixi (XVIII o‘rtalari- XIX asr o‘rtalari). - Т.: Tamaddun, 2022.
6. A.Ziyo. O‘zbek davlatchiligi tarixi (Eng qadimgi dvrдан Rossiya bosqiniga qadar) -Т:Sharq, 2000.
7. O‘zbekiston Milliy ensiklopediyasi Toshkent. Davlat ilmiy nashriyoti.

⁵Ж.М.Шодиев. Бухоро амирлиги давлатчилигининг ривожланиши. – Тошкент.; ТДЮИ “Тезкор нашр марказида”. 2010. Б – 45-46.